

FEED AND CONTAMINANTS UNIT (FEEDCO)

Internal Report

Report on the effects of food processing on the occurrence of mercury (Hg/Me-Hg) in fish

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1. Introduction and high level summary

In reply to the revised maximum levels for mercury in fish, ONSSA¹ (Office National de Sécurité Sanitaire des produits) of Morocco sent to the EC (European Commission, DG SANTE) a letter with comments related to the effects of food processing on the mercury content of fish and on its bioaccessibility, including 10 references to scientific publications which were not included in the 2012 CONTAM Opinion on the risk for public health related to the presence of mercury (Hg) and methylmercury (Me-Hg) in food.

In the 2012 CONTAM Opinion, the effects of food processing on the occurrence of mercury in fish were assessed. Most of the publications, to which ONSSA letter refers, are more recent.

EFSA was asked to check whether these publications contain new information with regard to the impact of cooking and processing on the occurrence of mercury in fish.

This internal report provides a high level summary on the effects of processing on mercury content in fish from the 2012 CONTAM Opinion and from the 8 more recent studies, plus 2 older, reported in the letter from ONSSA.

- The majority of the studies cited in the ONSSA letter reported that the bioaccessible percentage of Hg and Me-Hg decreases when fish is subjected to food processing. This was demonstrated for all the fish species analysed and for the most common cooking practices (i.e. steaming, frying, roasting etc.).
- One study reported that Total-Hg (T-Hg) decreased in grilling and frying for several fish species, while Organic-Hg (O-Hg) was reduced in all culinary practices independently by the fish species.
- Some studies showed that the presence of additives like lignin or a combination of ingredients like onions and broccoli used in specific fish meal can reduce the bioaccessible fraction of mercury species respect to the raw fish consumption.
- Other studies reported risk-benefits coming from a combination of effects between essential elements present in fish like Selenium, and toxic ones, can lower the hazard of Hg intake with fish consumption and therefore need to be considered as well for more realistic scenario in future risk assessments.
- The main findings from the studies cited in the letter are aligned with the 2012 CONTAM Opinion and show that there is little impact of cooking or processing on the content of mercury in food.
- Evidence that fish processing may decrease the bioaccessibility of mercury can only be found in vitro digestion models.

¹ <http://www.onssa.gov.ma/fr/>

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2. Effects of food processing and mercury content (EFSA CONTAM Panel, 2012):

The EFSA CONTAM Panel Opinion 2012 states that mercury in food is stable and resistant to the effects generally during food processing. Procedures like skinning or trimming of fish do not reduce the mercury content of the fillet portion, because the mercury is bound to the muscle part of the animal rather than skin and adipose tissue. Moreover, the total amount of mercury in fish remains relatively unchanged after cooking, and the slight changes in mercury that may occur are comparatively insignificant and generally do not need to be considered when estimating dietary exposure.

The Opinion cited several studies on the topic. Some of them indicate that frying or baking might slightly increase the mercury content, probably due to the weight loss combined with oil absorption (Chicourel, 2001; Burger, 2003; Perelló, 2008). Others indicate a reduction in mercury content probably due to the volatility of methylmercury during cooking (Farias, 2010). Some studies also used in vitro gastrointestinal digestion techniques to make preliminary assessments with respect to mercury bioavailability (Torres-Escribano, 2011; Maulvault, 2011). In this regard, it was generally reported a reduction that varies between 40% and 60% in the bioaccessible fraction of mercury in fish after cooking procedures. Overall, in vitro studies and studies looking at the impact of cooking and processing show that there is little impact of cooking or processing on the content of mercury in foods and so data for mercury in raw foods are suitable to use for dietary exposure estimates.

In addition:

The CONTAM Panel used a conservative approach to calculate methylmercury dietary exposure by assuming that 100 % of mercury in fish is in the form of methylmercury. However, in order to ensure that dietary exposure to inorganic mercury was not underestimated, 20 % of total mercury in fish was simultaneously assumed to be inorganic mercury when calculating inorganic mercury dietary exposure.

In line with JECFA, the CONTAM Panel established a tolerable weekly intake (TWI) for inorganic mercury of 4 µg/kg b.w., expressed as mercury and established a TWI for methylmercury of 1.3 µg/kg b.w.

The Opinion only focuses on the risks related to dietary inorganic mercury and methylmercury exposure and does not assess the nutritional benefits linked to certain foods (e.g. fish and other seafood).

The estimated exposure to inorganic mercury in Europe from the diet alone did not exceed the TWI established.

3. List of studies in the ONSSA letter and not cited in the CONTAM Panel 2012 opinion:

- **Meirio et al. (2016)**

This study evaluated the influence of different culinary practices (boiling, frying, grilling) and seasoning (salt, lemon, combined) on the Hg levels (Total and Organic) found in three marine fish species (Scomber scombrus, Dicentrarchus labrax, Aphanopus carbo).

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The authors showed that cooking affects the Hg levels in a species dependent manner. With the exception of *D. labrax*, Total-Hg (T-Hg) decreased in grilling and frying, while Organic-Hg (O-Hg) decreased in all culinary practices.

The authors concluded that since O-Hg is the major portion of Hg in fish muscle and all culinary practices removed O-Hg, setting consumption thresholds in terms of T-Hg in raw tissue seems protective and adequate.

- **Afonso et al. (2015a)** report that grilling and roasting procedures are healthier than raw fish consumption, because they lead to higher Selenium/Mercury molar ratios and Selenium bioaccessible fractions.

In this study a risk–benefit assessment of raw and cooked meagre (*A. regius*) on the basis of the bioaccessibility of Se, Hg, Me-Hg and omega-3 fatty acids data was carried out.

The meagre were cultivated in earth ponds in an Aquaculture unit located in Portugal. A total of 66 fish (average weight 600 g) were used in the study.

The authors stated that the Me-Hg percentage of the total bioaccessible mercury ranged from ca. 65% in grilled meagre to 100% in raw meagre. In all cases the bioaccessible Hg and Me-Hg percentages in cooked fish samples were found to be lower or similar with respect to the raw fish samples. This result is aligned with the CONTAM Panel Opinion (2012), which states that the oral bioavailability of Me-Hg from raw fish is higher than 80%.

It was remarked that cooking methods, in particular grilling or roasting, can lead to a decrease of the bioaccessibility of mercury.

The authors showed that all molar Se:Hg ratios were higher than 1 and all Se-HBVs (Selenium-Health Benefit Values) were positive, regardless of being calculated with the Hg or the Me-Hg contents.

Furthermore, they indicated a lower danger of the Me-Hg content to health as a result of the consumption of this fish species, since the amount of Se is high enough to overcome the negative effects of Hg.

To conclude, the authors claimed that grilling and roasting are healthier culinary treatments, given their higher Se:Hg molar ratios and Se-HBVs in the bioaccessible fraction.

- **Afonso et al. (2015b)** showed that bioaccessibility of both mercury forms considerably decreases in cooked and even more in canned tuna.

This study is a follow up of risk-benefit on Se, Hg, and methylmercury (Me-Hg) levels in raw, cooked (boiled and grilled), and canned tuna (*Thunnus* spp.).

With the purpose of learning about the effect of culinary process and bioaccessibility, twenty five cans of tuna (*Thunnus* spp.) in olive oil and twenty five in water (*Thunnus* spp.) were acquired from different Portuguese grocery stores. In addition, five samples of fresh tuna fish (*Thunnus* spp.), each containing

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three steaks of the same fish (average weight of each steak was 300 g), were purchased from five different Portuguese grocery stores.

Their content was determined before and after an *in vitro* digestion, thereby enabling the calculation of the respective bioaccessibility percentages.

The authors showed that cooking and processing treatments associated with harsher thermal treatments, such as canning and grilling, led to a decrease of Hg bioaccessibility in average (39%-48%), more pronounced in canned tuna (<20%).

Like in the other study (Afonso et al. 2015a), the authors' findings in terms of risk-benefits are similar. Given that all molar Se: Me-Hg ratios were higher than one (ranging from 10 up to 74) and all Se-HBVs were positive, the authors reported a low Me-Hg health hazard as a result of canned and cooked tuna consumption.

- **Afonso et al. (2018)**

In this specific study, the composition of raw and cooked gilthead seabream (*Sparus aurata*) was analysed. The bioaccessibility of several elements and substances including mercury (Hg), and methylmercury (Me-Hg) in raw and cooked fish was studied by an *in vitro* model.

The authors reported that the average percentage of Hg (and Me-Hg) available for intestinal absorption for the raw fish data 80-89% (and 79-99%) was reduced by cooking, especially by grilling, 39% (60%) and roasting, 38% (55%).

- **Jadán Piedra et al. (2016)** is in line with what stated in EFSA opinion. It may add some new info on the list of dietary components that reduces the bioaccessibility of Hg forms in fish.

This study explored dietary components that reduce the quantity of soluble (bioaccessible) mercury after digestion. The authors evaluated the effects of 28 compounds on solubility of inorganic mercury and methylmercury in aqueous solution after *in vitro* gastrointestinal digestion.

The food samples consisted of swordfish (*Xiphias gladius*) and yellowfin tuna (*Thunnus albacares*) samples that were purchased at various stores in the city of Valencia.

The main findings of the authors are shown in the figures below. Figure 3 shows the effects of the dietary compounds on the bioaccessibility of Hg in swordfish, while figure 4 focuses on tuna.

The results obtained indicate that most of the compounds assayed reduced the soluble fraction of Hg(II) and Me-Hg in aqueous solutions, and many of them reduce the fraction of Hg that is solubilised during digestion of seafood products and could therefore be classified as good candidates for the design of strategies aimed at reducing oral bioavailability of Hg.

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Fig. 3. Effect of the dietary compounds on the bioaccessibility of Hg in samples of swordfish [without addition (dark grey), with addition of the compound at the low concentration (light grey) and with addition of the high concentration of the compound (white)]. Values expressed in mg/kg (mean \pm SD, n = 4). Asterisks indicate significant differences in the bioaccessibility of Hg in samples of swordfish in the presence of the compound with respect to the bioaccessibility of Hg without addition of the compound (**, $p \leq 0.001$; *, $0.001 < p < 0.05$). CMC: carboxy methylcellulose; HPC: hydroxypropylcellulose; HPMC: hydroxypropylmethylcellulose; MC: methylcellulose.

Fig. 4. Effect of the dietary compounds on the bioaccessibility of Hg in samples of tuna [without addition (dark grey), with addition of the compound at the low concentration (light grey) and with addition of the high concentration of the compound (white)]. Values expressed in mg/kg (mean \pm SD, n = 4). Asterisks indicate significant differences in the bioaccessibility of Hg in samples of tuna in the presence of the compound with respect to the bioaccessibility of Hg without addition of the compound (**, $p \leq 0.001$; *, $0.001 < p < 0.05$). CMC: carboxy methylcellulose; HPC: hydroxypropylcellulose; HPMC: hydroxypropylmethylcellulose; MC: methylcellulose.

The authors concluded that the incorporation of cellulose derivatives, tannic acid, lignin or pectin in the diet, either in the form of supplements or else added to foodstuffs, may provide solutions for reducing the oral bioavailability of Hg. However, they noted that it is necessary to evaluate whether this effect observed in vitro is confirmed in vivo.

- Marmelo et al. (2020)** reported an overall decrease of the Hg bioaccessible fractions with cooking procedures. The authors also looked at interactions of ingredients of a complete meal, associated with an increase of bioaccessible Hg, in order to have more realistic scenarios for risk evaluations.

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The study aimed to evaluate the effect of different ingredients and cooking processes on mercury (Hg) and cadmium (Cd) bioaccessibility in complete meals of tuna (*Thunnus* spp.) and edible crab (*Cancer pagurus*), respectively.

Tuna (*Thunnus* spp., $n = 5$) and edible crab (*Cancer pagurus*, $n = 5$) were purchased in a local supermarket in Spain.

The authors presented different Hg content and bioaccessibility before and after in vitro digestion for each specific meal with tuna are shown.

Overall, Hg bioaccessibility percentages were always below 50% in tuna meals (raw, stewed without and with the addition of ingredients), indicating that the amount of Hg that can be absorbed by the body after digestion is well below the amount of Hg ingested.

The data showed that stewing resulted in a significant reduction of Hg bioaccessibility (13%) in relation to the values observed after the in vitro digestion of raw tuna. pointing out, that cooking is an excellent strategy to efficiently mitigate human exposure do Hg through seafood consumption.

The authors pointed out that the addition of ingredients increased Hg bioaccessibility up to 31% with respect to the stewed tuna. With this result, they highlighted the importance to include the effects of different culinary treatments (e.g., stewing, boiling/steaming, grilling and frying) and interactions with ingredients for a complete meal in order to have more realistic scenarios for dietary exposures and recommendations.

The authors also showed that the overall Hg bioaccessibility of stewed tuna with or without ingredients is always lower than raw tuna. This from an external point of view confirms that the assumption of raw fish data is suitable to use for dietary exposure estimates.

- **Liao et al. 2019** reported an overall decrease of the Hg bioaccessible fractions with cooking procedures. The study also reported, based on in vitro and vivo studies, that Me-Hg demethylation reactions may occur in the gastrointestinal tract. The authors concluded that the bioaccessibility of Hg^{2+} and Me-Hg is not entirely related to their initial concentrations in the food samples, but more studies are needed to clarify the conversion mechanisms.

The study investigates Hg speciation in cooked seafood after gastric and intestinal digestion. Nine types of seafood were sampled from local markets and grocery stores in Guangzhou City, China.

The objectives of the study are as follows: (1) to consider the effects of various cooking processes on Hg for different species of seafood using a mass balance calculation; (2) to determine the distribution of Hg speciation in bioaccessible digestion via physiologically based-extraction in vitro testing; and (3) to ascertain the reactions pertaining to the demethylation or methylation of Hg during gastrointestinal digestion by conducting in vivo experiments with mice.

The in vivo experiments were carried out using 36 mice including the 4 used as control. To evacuate the contents of the gut, the mice were prevented from eating anything for 1 day with the exception of drinking ultrapure water before the Hg exposure. The test groups were fed by gavage with Hg^{2+} and Me-Hg (1.5 mL; $5.0 \mu g L^{-1}$), respectively. The whole stomachs and intestines were sampled at 0.25, 0.5, 1.0, and 2.0 h after exposure, respectively.

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The in vitro test methods were performed in the digestion experiments with Me-Hg and Hg²⁺ aqueous solutions, namely, in vitro gametogenesis (IVG), the Solubility Bioavailability Research Consortium (SBRC) test, and the German Institute for Standardization (DIN) test. The authors reported that the gastrointestinal bioaccessible concentration of total Hg was lower than that in the seafood matrices in general. The reduced bioaccessibility percentages of total Hg in seafood after soaking, boiling, steaming, baking, and frying were 4%, 17%, 23%, 28%, and 42%, respectively. The authors verified that the main route of Hg loss during cooking was volatilization, and further that Hg²⁺ was more readily reduced than Me-Hg. The different culinary processes decreased the amount of bioaccessible Hg in the following order: raw > soaked > boiled > steamed > baked > fried. Additionally, the reduced percentage of bioaccessible Hg²⁺ after cooking was on average of 16%, which was slightly lower than that of Me-Hg (on average, 19%).

It was also reported that the contents of Hg²⁺ and Me-Hg in some types of seafood after gastrointestinal digestion were much higher than those in the food matrices in this study. According to the authors this might be due to reactions of methylation and demethylation of Hg which occurs during the digestion and alters the content of Hg²⁺ and Me-Hg.

Through various in vitro tests and in vivo gastrointestinal digestion experiments on mice, the authors proved that the methylation of Hg might take place in the gastric tract, whereas the demethylation of Hg primarily might take place during intestinal digestion.

Since it was not clear how the mechanisms of Hg methylation or de-methylation in seafood in the gastrointestinal tract works, the authors concluded that further studies on the specific mechanisms of Hg demethylation and methylation during gastrointestinal digestion are essential for more accurate assessments of Hg risk.

- **Alves et al. 2018** reported that for a large numbers of fish species and samples, Hg bioaccessible fractions were lower after cooking procedures. Furthermore, the authors reported that the risk-benefit between essential and toxic elements should be considered for future guidelines regarding seafood consumption, in order to provide more realistic information.

In the study the oral bioaccessibility of several essential and toxic elements (Se, As, Cd, Hg, Cu, I, Mn, Fe) was investigated in raw and cooked commercially available seafood species from European markets.

Nine seafood species were collected in different European markets including hake (*Merluccius australis*), tuna (*Katsuwonus pelamis*), monkfish (*Lophius piscatorius*), mackerel (*Scomber scombrus*), plaice (*Pleuronectes platessa*), mussel (*Mytilus edulis*), octopus (*Octopus vulgaris*), shrimp (*Litopenaeus vannamei*) and one seaweed species (*Laminaria digitata*). All samples were collected in different seasons between April 2014 and November 2015.

To assess the in vitro digestion efficiency, total protein levels were determined using an FP-528 DSP LECO nitrogen analyser (LECO, St. Joseph, USA). Protein levels were measured in wet weight (raw and steamed) – before digestion (BD), and in the bioaccessible (BIO) and non-bioaccessible (NBIO) fractions. The calibration standard curve was performed with EDTA following the methodology described by SaintDenis and Goupy (2004) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2003.10.090>.

In Fig.2 below shows Hg and Me-Hg % bioaccessibility on 5 predatory fish species (raw Vs steamed) after in vitro digestion:

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Fig. 2. Bioaccessibility (%) of toxic (A – mercury, B – methylmercury) elements in raw and steamed samples (average \pm standard deviation). * represent differences between raw and steamed for each seafood species (t-student for dependent variables, $p < .05$)

The authors also made a complete risk-benefit assessment considering all the molar ratios between essential and toxic elements. Here it is only reported the outcome of the mercury/selenium ratio.

In the study, all five predatory species had Se:Hg and Se:Me-Hg molar ratios above 1, showing that Se molar content exceeded Hg molar content. The analysed seafood species presented positive Se-HBV values, suggesting that consuming these five seafood species can reduce the risks associated with the inhibition of selenoenzymes by Me-Hg.

Regarding Hg the authors concluded that, Me-Hg revealed low bioaccessibility in all fish species, Me-Hg was reduced in steamed seafood, thus lowering the health risks when seafood is consumed with this culinary practice. A low health hazard was associated to the five predatory species consumption as shown by the positive Se-HBV and high molar Se:Me-Hg ratio.

The authors also remarked that, food risk and benefit assessment should take into consideration the diversity of seafood species, the effects of culinary treatment and the bioaccessibility of the compounds under study to provide more accurate indications about health effects to consumers, refinements of food safety legislation and guidelines for consumers regarding seafood consumption, thus minimizing under- or overestimations of risks/benefits, and providing more realistic information.

- Rasmussen et al. (2007)** reported that mercury concentration per gram of tuna tissue was significantly higher following canning and cooking. Based on a pragmatic point of view, the higher Hg levels in processed fish are probably due to a loss of moisture and weight during cooking, which cause mercury to concentrate more heavily in the meat.

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In this study a total of 56 cans, 20 cans with olive oil, 20 cans with spring water, and 16 cans raw packed (no added liquid), containing meat from either the dorsal loin or the ventral flap of 10 troll-caught albacore tuna were tested for total mercury concentration prior to and after canning and retort cooking.

The authors reported that the average concentrations of total mercury were: 0.17 ppm (range 0.09–0.24 ppm) in the pre-canned samples and 0.21 ppm (range 0.10–0.33 ppm) in the post-canned samples. This means an increase of 23% in average between pre-canned and post-canned tuna. In addition they showed the decreases of moisture and fat content, which was in average 5.8% and 3.6% respectively, accompanied by total weight loss of 12.8% and an average increment on protein content equal to 10% from pre-canned to post-canned samples.

The authors conclusion stated that it was not possible to correlate the increment in mercury content with the weight losses in moisture and lipid or with the increment of protein found after canning.

Among the possible explanations behind this results there could be the experiment setup for the Hg testing, which was found to be inadequate, not considering the weight losses of fish after processing.

In the material and methods section, paragraph 2.3 of the study it is stated that a two-grams aliquots were taken from each sample of fishes and then analysed for the Hg content following a standard procedure. This statement implies that equal amount of raw and processed fishes (cooked and/or canned with different ingredients) were considered when evaluating the Hg content.

It was known a decrease in weight (on average 12.8%) between pre-canned and post-canned fish samples coming from the moisture and fat losses, which was not taken into account when preparing the samples for the mercury content.

With the authors taking equal amounts of raw fish, which include moisture and fat other than protein, and processed fish, which has lost most of the moisture and fat leaving mainly protein, there is the wrong assumption to consider both fish groups as comparable. The experiment setup shown in section 2.3 is basically evaluating the same weight of samples with an intrinsic different concentration of mercury.

The authors found an higher content of mercury on processed fish, probably because of its higher concentration in the meat driven by moisture and fat losses.

- **Aizpurua et al. (1997)** doesn't add any relevant info from the fish process and mercury content perspective.

This study evaluates the efficiency of cysteine to remove mercury from sliced and minced shark.

The authors claimed that treatment with 0.5% cysteine at pH 2.0–2.5 and subsequent washing with sodium chloride (5%) failed to remove the mercury from the sliced shark. The efficiency of 0.5% cysteine at pH 7.0 in removing mercury from minced shark was 40–45% (dry material), obtained by two of the three methods studied.

The authors concluded that the removal rate of 0.5% was considered relatively low for it failed to attend to the practical proposal of decontaminating species of fish highly contaminated by mercury.

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Abbreviations

As	arsenic
CONTAM	Contaminant unit in EFSA
Cd	Cadmium
Cu	copper
EC	European Commission
EFSA	European Food and Safety Authority
Fe	Iron
Hg	Inorganic mercury form
Me-Hg	Methyl mercury (organic form)
Mn	Manganese
ONSSA	Office National de Sécurité Sanitaire des produits
TWI	Tolerable Weekly intake

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Appendix A

Power point slides

ONSSA letter to EC

- EC Regulation Annex (2021)² lower the ML of mercury (**0.3 mg/Kg ww**) for muscle meat of some fish species (anchovies, sardine, carp, trout etc.)
- Concerns about the new ML of mercury in fish which is going to considerably **reduce the fish export** in Europe
- Reconsider the new ML based on **new studies finding on mercury levels and fish processing**

1) COMMISSION REGULATION (EC) No 1881/2006,
2) POOL/E2/2021/10382/10382 EN ANNEX

2

Studies cited in ONSSA letter to EC

evidences on in vitro tests about:

- **decreasing of the Hg bioaccessible fractions (Hg and Me-Hg) during cooking procedure** and even more in canned fish
- cooking procedures are healthier than raw fish consumption given the **higher bioaccessible Selenium/Mercury molar ratios.**

Liao et al. (2019) Afonso et al. (2015b) Afonso et al. (2018) Alves et al. (2018), Afonso et al. (2015a)

3

Effects of food processing on the occurrence of mercury in fish

Studies cited in ONSSA letter to EC

evidences on in vitro tests about:

- **interactions with ingredients in** complete fish vegetables meals decrease the bioaccessible mercury
- **list of dietary components** (lignin, tannic acid etc.) **that reduces the bioaccessibility of mercury** forms in fish.

Jadán Piedra et al. (2016), Marmelo et al. (2020)

4

Studies cited in ONSSA letter to EC

evidences about:

- Slight decreased in mercury content after cooking, setting consumption thresholds in terms of **mercury in raw tissue seems adequate.**
- **mercury concentration** per gram of tuna tissue **higher** following canning and cooking. Probably **due to a loss of moisture and weight during cooking**, which might cause mercury to concentrate more heavily in the meat.

Meirio et al. (2016), Rasmussen et al. (2007)

5

Effects of food processing on the occurrence of mercury in fish

EFSA 2012 opinion on Hg

- **mercury** in food **remains stable** and resistant to all kinds of effects encountered **during food processing**
- reduction in mercury content probably due to the volatility of methylmercury during cooking
- **bioaccessible fraction of mercury** could be **reduced** between 40% and 60% in fish **after cooking** procedures
- data for **mercury in raw foods** are **suitable** to use for **dietary exposure estimates**

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Conclusions

1) EFSA (2012) Scientific Opinion on the risk for public health related to the presence of mercury and methylmercury in food

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